

**RUPTURE OF CARBON FIBRE REINFORCED PLASTICS (T300-914)
COMPOSITE MATERIALS :
INFLUENCE OF INITIAL FIRST PLY FAILURES ON THE FATIGUE BEHAVIOR**

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ABSTRACT

Carbon fibre reinforced plastic is used in an increasing number of aerospace structures and the damages influence on the material's properties must be determined. First ply failure consequences on the material's fatigue behavior are experimentally studied for $(0, 90)$, $(0, 90, \pm 45)$ and $(0_3, 90, \pm 45)$ lay-ups by comparison of undamaged specimens and specimens with initial damage either in the 90° plies or in the 0° plies. Initial presence of ply failures in the 90° plies influences damage evolution and makes the stiffness reduction faster ; stress concentrations due to these cracks may also create more fibre's breakings ; life time is equal or longer and this may be explained by modifications of the 0° plies properties. If there is initial damage in the 0° plies, Poisson's ratio becomes smaller, initial stiffness reduction is similar and life time is very shorter.

INTRODUCTION

Carbon fibre reinforced plastic composites are frequently used in aeronautical and aerospace industry, fields in which the notion of weight gain becomes particularly significant. To facilitate design beyond first ply failure (FPF), it is necessary to study the influence of such initial damage on the residual material properties, and in particular the static and fatigue properties. Many authors [1, 2, 3] have studied and described damage mechanisms and damage evolution during fatigue tests, the aim of this present study is to make a comparison between the behaviour of specimens with or without initial damage.

EXPERIMENTAL ASPECT

The material tested was T300-914, the lay-ups studied were the following : $(0, 90)_S$, $(0, 90, \pm 45)_S$, $(0_3, 90, \pm 45)_S$ and procedure was as follow :

- determination of mechanical properties of the undamaged material in the two principal directions, by tensile tests ; study of the FPF damage propagation during the steady loading.
- specimens were produced with a fixed damage state by steady loading at about $90\% \sigma_R$, either in the 90° plies, or in the 0° plies. These latter samples were obtained by tensile tests on large specimens of $(90, 0)_S$, $(90, 0, \pm 45)_S$, $(90_3, 0, \pm 45)_S$, they were cut in the transverse direction to obtain the above mentionned specimens. The damaged material was tested in traction in order to determine its mechanical properties.
- fatigue tests were conducted to different load levels (about 70 %, 80 % σ_R) with damaged and undamaged specimens. During these tests, the evolution of the mechanical properties was followed to allow correlation with damage propagation, and fatigue life times were determined.

Measurements of longitudinal and transverse strains were made with strain gauges during the steady load tests, during the first thousands fatigue cycles and with extensometer during all the fatigue tests. Replicas were made on sections of the specimens after different periods of fatigue loading to observe the damage propagation and the specimens were observed after failure by optical and scanning electron microscopy.

The specimens tested were 200 mm long and 17 mm wide and fatigue tests were performed in a tension-tension mode at 10 Hz with a sinusoidal loading pattern at a stress ratio $R = 0.1$. Maximum fatigue stresses were 75 % σ_R for the $(0, 90)_S$ specimens, 70 % and 80 % σ_R for the $(0, 90, \pm 45)_S$ specimens and 78 % σ_R for the $(0_3, 90, \pm 45)_S$ specimens.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Static Properties

Specimens with initial damage in the 0° plies were tested by tensile tests. There was no significant evolution for the Young's modulus and failure stress, but the Poisson's ratio decreased significantly as soon as

there was FPF damage in the 0° plies ; this decrease was about 20 % for $(0, 90, \pm 45)_S$ and $(0_3, 90, \pm 45)_S$ and about 30 % for $(0, 90)_S$ between undamaged material and samples which had been previously transversally tested at 90 % σ_R . This may be explained by the presence of ruptures in a parallel direction with the fibres, which reduced the 0° plies Poisson's ratio and modified the constraint effects described by Stinchomb and al [4] .

Fatigue Properties

Figures 1, 2 and 3 represent the evolution of the normalized Young's modulus during fatigue tests. For the sample without initial damage, the curves present the same general trend for the different lay-ups. Initially, there was a rapid decrease, which corresponded with the observation of an increase in damage of the inner plies (rupture in the 90° , $+45^\circ$ and -45° plies, delaminations between the different plies). There was then a steady phase during which modulus changes were less important and the damage evolution in the inner plies continued slowly, at the beginning of this phase we obtained for the different ply directions a crack density which did not increase afterwards. These densities were the same for the two values of maximum stress used with the $(0, 90, \pm 45)_S$ samples and they may have corresponded to the characteristic damage state studied by Reifsmider [4] . Delaminations increased also, but total delamination was not observed, except for the $(0_3, 90, \pm 45)_S$ specimens between the 90° and $+45^\circ$ plies after about 3000 cycles. During the last stage, there was an important and rapid decrease of modulus which led quickly to the failure of the specimen.

Figure 1. Evolution of normalized Young's modulus for the $(0, 90)_S$ laminae ; maximal fatigue stress value is $0,75 \sigma_R$.

Figure 2 . Evolution of normalized Young's modulus for the $(0, 90, \pm 45)_s$ laminates ; maximal fatigue stress value is $0,6 \sigma_R$.

Figure 3 . Evolution of normalized Young's modulus for the $(0_3, 90, \pm 45)_s$ laminates ; maximal stress value is $0,78 \sigma_R$.

If we suppose that there is no damage in the 0° plies, it is possible to evaluate the fall in Young's modulus which corresponds to damage in the other plies : for a $(0, 90)_s$ lay-up, and if there is no delamination, we can

obtain, using the results of Garrett and Bailey [5] :

$$\frac{1}{E_e} = \frac{1}{E_c} + \frac{2}{L E_o \sqrt{\phi}} \left(2 - \frac{E_o}{E_c} \right) \left(1 - e^{-\sqrt{\phi} \frac{L}{2}} \right) \quad (1)$$

$$\phi = \frac{2 E_c G_t}{E_o E_{90} b^2} \quad (2)$$

where E_e , E_c , E_o , E_{90} are the Young's moduli respectively of damaged specimens, undamaged specimens, 0° plies and 90° plies, G_t is the shear modulus of the transverse ply in the y direction, b the 0° plies thickness and L the average spacing between two cracks.

If there is delaminations, but only at the end of the ruptures in the 90° plies (which is observed), we propose to take into account this phenomena and modify equation (1) such as :

$$\frac{1}{E_e} = \frac{1}{E_c} + \frac{1}{L E_o} \left(2 - \frac{E_o}{E_c} \right) + \frac{2}{L E_o \sqrt{\phi}} \left(2 - \frac{E_o}{E_c} - e^{-\sqrt{\phi} \left(\frac{L-l}{2} \right)} \right)$$

where l is the average length of delamination.

For the other lay-ups, we do not have the value of E_e in which appear the different types of damage (rupture in the inner plies and delaminations), but it is possible, using the ply discount technique to obtain the minimum value of the normalized Young's modulus if there is no damage in the 0° plies : $\frac{E_e}{E_c} = \frac{E_o b}{E_c (b+d)}$ where (b+d) is the specimen thickness. If we compare the values measured during the steady phase and these obtained by considering that there is no damage in the 0° plies (table 1), we can see for the $(0, 90)_s$ and $(0_3, 90, \pm 45)_s$ lay-ups that it is necessary to consider damage in these plies (fibres breaks, debonding between fibre and matrix, matrix cracking) to explain the fall in Young's modulus; It is not necessary to assure the development of damage in order to explain the $(0, 90, \pm 45)_s$ lay-up behaviour, but this does not mean that it does not occur.

The main differences in Young's modulus evolution between specimens with and without initial damage.

TABLE 1

Normalized Young's modulus particular values for the different laminates.

normalized Young's modulus lay-up	undamaged material	if only the 0° plies carry the load	measured during the step phase	rate of damage in the 0° plies if they carry alone the load
$(0, 90)_s$	1	.93	.82	12%
$(0, 90, \pm 45)_s$	1	.65	.88	*
$(0_3, 90, \pm 45)_s$ without initial damage	1	.84	.75	11%
$(0_3, 90, \pm 45)_s$ with initial damage	1	.84	.68	21%

* in this case, a damage in the 0° plies is not necessary

If there is initial damage in the 90° plies, one of the main differences appears during the first cycles. The initial fall in modulus is much faster and the steady phase begins earlier. A comparison between the different types of damage evolution allow us to verify that the damage states in the inner plies are similar at the beginning of the steady phase, and that for $(0, 90)_s$ and $(0, 90, \pm 45)_s$ lay-ups, the presence of initial damage modifies the material as if it has been loaded by fatigue test during a number of cycles corresponding to the first part of the curve. For the $(0_3, 90, \pm 45)_s$ specimens, it is not easy to correlate initial damage with a particular number of cycles. Such a difference during the first cycles does not exist for $(0, 90)_s$ specimens if there is initial damage in the 0° plies and the first parts of the curves are very similar.

Another difference may exist during the steady phase. If there is initial damage in the 90° plies, for $(0, 90)_s$ and $(0, 90, \pm 45)_s$ lay-ups, no significant difference was noticed for the Young's modulus values of specimens with and without initial damage, and the evolution of damage in the inner plies was similar for the two types of specimen. For the $(0, 90)_s$ lay-ups, for which it is necessary to consider damage in the 0° plies, these observations lead to the conclusion that these damage processes must be very similar in the two cases. It is different for $(0_3, 90, \pm 45)_s$ lay-ups, the

two normalized Young's modulus values obtained during this phase were very different (for the specimens with initial damage, they were about 10 % lower). Observations of damage evolution (Figure 4) allow us to consider that this difference results from differences between the 0° plies damage states (there are a lot of failures in the 90° , $+45^\circ$ and -45° plies, and total delamination between the 90° and $+45^\circ$ plies). On photographs 1 and 2, we can see the aspects of the 0° plies faces which were against the 90° plies, after the failure of the specimens (these observations were made far from the failure zone). There are horizontal line which are matrix deposit and the average spacing of which corresponds to the distance between two cracks in the 90° plies. Near these lines are most of fibre failures and these fibre break are far more numerous for the specimens with initial damage. This presence of fibres failures near the transverse cracks describes by Jamison [6] explain the fall in Young's modulus under the

Figure 4 . Damage evolution in the inner plies for the $(0_3, 90, \pm 45)_s$ laminates ; maximal stress value is $0,78 \sigma_R$.
 Right hand : sample without initial damage
 Left hand : sample with initial damage

Photography 1 . 0° plies face which was against the 90° plies for a $(0_3, 90, \pm 45)_S$ sample without initial damage.

Photography 2 . 0° plies face which was against the 90° plies for a $(0_3, 90, \pm 45)_S$ sample with initial damage.

level without damage in 0° plies and can also explain the difference of values during the steady phase. To explain the presence of more fibre breakage for specimens with initial damage, it is necessary to consider damage evolution before the steady phase. During the first thousands cycles, the crack density in the 90° plies increases only slowly in the specimens with initial damage, but delamination between the 90° and 0° plies are less important for these specimens. So, delamination at crack ends reduces the effect of stress concentrations. Then, presence of cracks in the 90° plies with or without delamination lead to a greater damage state in the 0° plies for the specimens with initial damage.

For the $(0, 90)_S$ specimens with initial damage in the 0° plies, the beginning of the steady phase was similar, but rapidly, the Young's modulus abruptly fall, which was followed by another steady phase. The Young's modulus fall continued in steps. During the tests, it was possible to see packets of broken fibres in the 0° plies. Breakage of packets of fibres may be explained by a non uniform stress distribution due to the presence of crack in parallel with fibres in the 0° plies.

For specimens with initial damage in the 90° plies, it was also possible to see on the photographs cracks parallel with the fibres in the 0° plies, which appeared during fatigue tests, these cracks may have a small influence on the Young's modulus by modification of the constraints effects, and a greater influence on the Poisson's ratio. This could explain the fall of this latter coefficient which was noticed at the beginning of the fatigue tests.

Fatigue Life

Table 2 shows fatigue lives for each specimen and the average fatigue life for each type of sample. In these cases where there was initial damage in the 90° plies, we can note that fatigue life was equal or longer than that of specimens without such damage. Fatigue tests were also made on $(0, 90, \pm 45)_S$ specimens with two maximum stress values and the difference disappeared with the highest value, if we compare the damage states obtained during the steady phase in these two cases, it is possible to note that they are similar and then, we consider that this difference of fatigue life arises essentially from the 0° plies differences. If we look at photographs 3 and 4, we can see that the pullout of fibres in the 0° plies was smaller and that bonding, between matrix and fibre were of a better quality when the specimens were initially overloaded. When the maximum fatigue stress value was higher, the initial static traction influence is smaller and the difference of 0° plies behaviour becomes less important.

When there is initial damage in the 0° plies, lifetime is very shorter and the results show considerable scatter. This may be explained by fibre packets breaking in the 0° plies early in the tests, these failures do not provide after the same cycles number for all the samples and this is due to the intrinsic dispersion of the fibre strength.

TABLE 2

Fatigue life of the different samples tested. Left hand : for each sample ;
Right hand : average for each types of samples. (versus thousand cycles).

	maximal stress (% σ_r)	sample without initial damage		sample with initial damage	
If initial damage is in the 90° plies					
$(0, 90)_s$	75	135 168 147 125	144	170 154 137	154
$(0, 90, \pm 45)_s$	70	60 57 54 56	59	76 80 68	73
$(0, 90, \pm 45)_s$	80	15 16 15,5 15	15.4	16 14 14.5	14.8
$(0_3, 90, \pm 45)_s$	78	106 89 78	91	104 92 84	93
If initial damage is in the 0° plies					
$(0, 90)_s$	75	135 168 125 147	144	85 30 76 52	61

Photography 3 . 0° plies rupture's facies for a $(0_3, 90, \pm 45)_s$ sample without initial damage.

Photography 4 . 0° plies rupture's facies for $(0_3, 90, \pm 45)_s$ sample with initial damage.

CONCLUSION

These results seem to show that the effects of an initial loading by static traction are of two kinds. Multiple failures in the 90° plies which influence damage evolution at the beginning of the test and produces changes in the Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio. This damage may also influence fibre breakage in the 0° plies by stress concentrations. Evolution in the 0° plies which modify loading between fibre and matrix and can influence lifetime. The consequences of FPF damage are greater for fatigue loading than for static loading, especially if this damage is in the 0° plies. As Hashin [7] proposes, it would be desirable to evaluate the stiffness reduction due to the cracks in the + 45° and - 45° plies to obtain a better analysis of the laminate behaviour.

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